

INTEGRATING SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING INTO CURRICULUM: CONTINUAL IMPROVEMENT USING CDIO FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to share with readers how the CDIO Framework can be used to drive continual improvement in one's program (diploma in Singapore Polytechnic's context). The CDIO Initiative is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating (hence the acronym CDIO) real-world systems and products. Throughout the world, CDIO Initiative collaborators have adopted CDIO as the framework of their curricular planning and outcome-based assessment. This paper will share a case study of how a diploma that adopted CDIO Framework had used it to integrate self-directed learning (SDL) in its 3-year curriculum, to better prepare students for the future world landscape where being competent means being able to acquire diverse knowledge from different fields to solve problems. The aim is to progressively prepare students from one who may lack self-confidence in his/her own capability to one that is capable of learning on his/her own and able to use self-directed learning skills in various workplace context, both simulated and real-world. The paper will provide the background of why SDL is being integrated, and the approach taken to start exposing students to the notion of SDL in Year 1 Semester 1 by requiring them to look up resources curated for their needs. The explicit teaching of SDL took place in Year 1 Semester 2 and was infused throughout 15 weeks of lesson in a skill-based module. The paper also provides clarifications of how relevant CDIO Standards were used to guide the design of various learning experiences for students to progressively develop the competency over their duration of study in the diploma. Work done for the past 3 years will be explained and how CDIO is used to drive the continual improvement process undertaken will be described.

Keywords: *Continual Improvement, CDIO, Self-Directed Learning, Program Evaluation*

Introduction

The CDIO Initiative is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating (hence the acronym CDIO) real-world systems and products. Throughout the world, CDIO Initiative collaborators have adopted CDIO as the framework of their curricular planning and outcome-based assessment (www.cdio.org). 2 key elements of the CDIO Framework are the CDIO Syllabus and the 12 CDIO Core Standards. The Framework is also supported by several optional standards.

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) from Singapore Polytechnic (SP) had been using the CDIO Framework to guide its curriculum redesign since 2007. Over the years various skills and attitudes had been integrated into the DCHE curriculum with guidance from the CDIO Syllabus and Standards, including teamwork and communication, critical thinking, global mindset, ethical reasoning; career awareness and more recently: self-directed learning (SDL), which started in Semester 2, Academic Year 2018.

This paper explains how the CDIO Standards are used to help the teaching team to continually improve the teaching of SDL competency to students over the last 4 years. Details of the efforts will not be covered here, and readers are referred to papers presented at past International CDIO Conferences (Wong & Cheah, 2022; Wong, Chua & Cheah, 2021; Cheah, 2020; Cheah, Wong & Yang, 2019).

CDIO and Continual Improvement

The 12 CDIO Core Standards are shown in Table 1. Descriptors and rationale for each standard is available at www.cdio.org. The main standard referenced in this paper is Standard 12 Program Evaluation, which is useful in guiding the curriculum review process with the aim of achieving continual improvement. The descriptor for Standard 12 states that:

Program evaluation is a judgment of the overall value of a program based on evidence of a program's progress toward attaining its goals. A CDIO program should be evaluated relative to these 12 CDIO Standards and any

optional standards that it has adopted. Evidence of overall program value can be collected with course evaluations, instructor reflections, entry and exit interviews, reports of external reviewers, and follow-up studies with graduates and employers. The evidence should be regularly reported back to instructors, students, program administrators, alumni, and other key stakeholders. This feedback forms the basis of decisions about the program and its plans for continuous improvement.

Table 1. The 12 CDIO Core Standards

CDIO Standard 1	The Context
Adoption of the principle that sustainable product, process, system, and service lifecycle development and deployment – Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating – are the context for engineering education	
CDIO Standard 2	Learning Outcomes
Specific, detailed learning outcomes for personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, system, and service building skills, as well as disciplinary knowledge, consistent with program goals and validated by program stakeholders	
CDIO Standard 3	Integrated Curriculum
A curriculum designed with mutually supporting disciplinary courses, with an explicit plan to integrate personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, system, and service building skills.	
CDIO Standard 4	Introduction to Engineering
An introductory course that provides the framework for engineering practice in product, process, system, and service building, and introduces essential personal and interpersonal skills and the rationale of sustainability in the context of engineering.	
CDIO Standard 5	Design-Implement Experiences
A curriculum that includes two or more design-implement experiences, including one at a basic level and one at an advanced level.	
CDIO Standard 6	Engineering Learning Workspaces
A physical learning environment that includes engineering workspaces and laboratories that support and encourage hands-on learning of product, process, system, and service building, disciplinary knowledge, and social learning, combined with a digital learning environment that includes on-line tools and spaces that support and enhance the quality of teaching and student learning.	
CDIO Standard 7	Integrated Learning Experiences
Integrated learning experiences that lead to the acquisition of disciplinary knowledge, as well as personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, system, and service building skills.	
CDIO Standard 8	Active Learning
Teaching and learning based on active and experiential learning methods.	
CDIO Standard 9	Enhancement of Faculty Competence
Actions that enhance faculty competence in personal and interpersonal skills, product, process, system, and service building skills, as well as disciplinary fundamentals.	
CDIO Standard 10	Enhancement of Faculty Teaching Competence
Actions that enhance faculty competence in providing integrated learning experiences, in using active and	

experiential learning methods, and in assessing student learning.	
CDIO Standard 11	Learning Assessment
Assessment of student learning in personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, system, and service building skills, as well as in disciplinary knowledge.	
CDIO Standard 12	Program Evaluation
A system that evaluates programs against these twelve standards and any optional standards adopted, and provides feedback to students, faculty, and other stakeholders for the purposes of continuous improvement.	

Why Integrate Self-Directed Learning?

Self-directed learning had been defined by Knowles (1975)) as “a process in which individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, to diagnose their learning needs, formulate learning goals, identify resources for learning, select and implement learning strategies, and evaluate learning outcomes”. SDL has been identified as the key approach for becoming a lifelong learner (Candy, 1991; Alexander, Kernohan. & McCullagh, 2004; Tunney & Bell, 2011). A meta-analytic review by Boyer et al (2014) on SDL research over 30 years, five countries, and across multiple academic disciplines provided a strong case for using SDL to promote lifelong learning skills in students.

The importance of lifelong learning, and hence the impetus to integrate SDL into our curriculum arisen our use of CDIO to actively scan the changing external environment that can impact teaching and learning, in particular with the ‘arrival’ of Industry 4.0. It was given further impetus with the launch of the SkillsFuture Initiative introduced by the Singapore Government in 2015 (<https://www.skillsfuture.gov.sg/>) where fostering a “culture that supports and celebrates lifelong learning” is one of the four key thrusts. The other three are: Help individuals make well-informed choices in education, training and careers, (2) Develop an integrated high-quality system of education and training that responds to constantly evolving needs, and (3) Promote employer recognition and career development based on skills and mastery. This initiative has far-reaching impact on all educational sectors, in particular the polytechnics, which aim is to prepare graduates for the workforce.

In SP, all diploma were reviewed to ensure alignment to the requirements of the skills framework(s) for the key stakeholders in the respective industry sector(s) the diploma is serving. To meet the need for lifelong learning, all diplomas are also required to integrate SDL into its curriculum. The Department of Educational Development (EDU) developed a generic model for SDL, as shown in Figure 1 for use by all diplomas. The SDL highlighted 2 key elements: mindset (growth mindset and intrinsic motivation) and skillset (comprising of plan, manage, review, evaluate and extend learning, governed by metacognition). Each diploma can adopt this generic model and further customized it to fit their own respective contexts.

Figure 1. The SP SDL Model

The remainder of this paper illustrate how the CDIO Syllabus and relevant Standards are being used to guide the integration of SDL into DCHE curriculum to the develop SDL competency among our students, and to continually improve the teaching and learning effort.

Importance of SDL in Chemical Engineering

DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) conducted environmental scanning on a regular basis to detect changes in the external operating environment that can affect the teaching of chemical engineering. With the advent of Industry 4.0, we recognized that with the adoption of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) technologies, the future job role and nature of tasks that our graduates may perform as process technicians will change (for details of this analysis, see Cheah & Yang, 2018). There will be new competencies to be developed, and existing competencies such as critical thinking need to be enhanced. For example, being able to think critically to discern good from bad data is important in light of massive process plant data captured by smart sensors throughout a chemical plant. Ability to understand issues from different perspectives had gained importance as one work with people of other disciplines, often via online platform, a point made apparent from the Covid-19 pandemic. New competencies such as virtual collaboration, teamworking and communicating effectively thus demand new ways of training our students who are accustomed to face-to-face instructions. With limited curriculum hours – which remained fixed in 3 years for diploma study – but always faced increasing pressure to make room for other non-engineering contents, meant that the technical coverage must be reduced but yet remained sufficient for students to exercise when in the workplace. SDL therefore becomes ever-more important as we leave out from the curriculum knowledge that students can learn on their own.

DCHE Course Structure to Develop SDL

We recognized that SDL is a high-order competency that needs to be build up gradually, and hence a phased approach is adopted, using our spiral curriculum course structure as shown in Figure 2. Note that Figure 2 shows

only the modules relevant to development of SDL designed based on CDIO Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum. It is worth bearing in mind that the same approach is used for integration and progressive development of *any* desired competency.

Figure 2. The DCHE Spiral Curriculum

The DCHE spiral curriculum starts with a rectangle shown as a mix of half-white and half-grey in Stage 1A. This is the ‘anchor’ module of *Introduction to Chemical Engineering* which is suggested in CDIO Standard 4. One of the key features of this standard is to introduce students to the profession. This module will then be the “springboard” to move into learning the rest of the modules in the diploma which centered around 2 pathways for preparing graduates for the chemical industry. One is via a “more standard” approach in chemical plant operation, where students either work in chemical laboratories or process plants. This is shown as 4 white rectangles in Figure 2, acquiring skills in laboratory analytical and/or investigative work as chemical plant process operations work over 4 semesters. The other pathway is the chemical product pathway, where skills in conceiving, designing, implementing and operating a product, process, system or service using chemical engineering principles. These are shown as 3 grey rectangles in Figure 2, over 3 semesters, ending with final year capstone project. In addition, students are expected to apply SDL skills during their internship, shown as the black rectangle in Figure 2.

Right from the beginning students are already exposed to the notion of SDL, although often not explicitly mentioned as such. This is done by getting students to read up factual information needed for their work in various modules. Much of these factual information were previous taught to students in lectures, but now converted as online resources for one’s own learning. Students are now guided in their assignments to make use of these materials for the work that they need to complete. This serves to sensitize them to the need to look up information that they needed.

The integration of SDL into the DCHE curriculum leverage of the 2 pathways mentioned earlier (Figure 2), with explicit teaching of SDL took place in the module *Laboratory & Process Skills 2* in Stage 1B. This module continues the preparation of students for laboratory investigative work using inquiry-based learning that started with *Laboratory & Process Skills 1* in Stage 1A. It then transitions into process operation skills to prepare students for work in chemical processing plants, using scenario-based learning. Teaching of SDL is carried out throughout the entire module.

With the spiral curriculum structure, when students progressed to Year 2, they will continue to hone their SDL competency in the chemical plant operation pathway, via more complex plant operations in module such as *Process Operations Skills 1* in Stage 2A with more scenario-based learning. They will also transfer the laboratory investigative skills to the chemical product design pathway that starts with the module *Introduction to Chemical Product Design* using project-based learning, also in Stage 2A. For their internship, students are expected to apply SDL skills in the workplace they are assigned to, the job scope can be wide-ranging depending of the nature of the company business, students (as interns) can be working in the laboratory or manufacturing facility involving in different tasks such as quality assurance and control, plant operation, work flow improvement, etc.

DCHE Approach to Integrate SDL using CDIO

In the DCHE approach, we also recognized the importance of leveraging other skills needed to support SDL, such as information literacy, resilience, etc) as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Elements of SDL Competency

As mentioned previously, the explicit teaching of DL took place in the Stage 1B module *Laboratory & Process Skills 2*. This is the module that the author played the lead role in designing using the CDIO Framework. As such, the rest of this paper presents the work done and continual improvement made to this module.

In addition, we also introduced an ‘operational’ model of SDL as shown in Figure 4, which we used to guide students along. Several features were made explicit in this model: the iterative nature when one goes through

the stage of identifying one’s learning need(s), writing learning goal(s), formulating learning strategies,

Figure 4. The DCHE SDL ‘Operational’ Model

monitoring and evaluating the learning process, and appraising the learning outcome(s) and assessing one’s progress towards attaining one’s state learning goal(s). The need to recognize and manage one’s emotion in the learning process, and the ability to transfer one’s SDL competency initially develop to other settings are also made explicit.

Lastly, to help students deal with the thinking skills behind the key steps in the learning process, and better appreciate the importance of metacognition, we also explicitly teach them various thinking heuristics, based on Sale’s Model of Thinking shown in Figure 5 (Sale, 2015).

Figure 5. Sale’s Model of Thinking

With all these ‘ingredients’ in place, we proceed to use the rest of the CDIO Standards to guide the module redesign effort to integrate SDL. We start with CDIO Standard 1 (The Context), which emphasized the need to consider learning settings that mimic real-world workplace requirements so that learning is meaningful for students. The learning outcomes (CDIO Standard 2) is written using Bloom’s taxonomy, taking reference from the CDIO Syllabus; and matched to the context in which SDL is introduced. We conducted a briefing during the first week, and 2 workshops using Active Learning methods (CDIO Standard 8) to explicitly teach our students the DCHE SDL Model and Sale’s Model of Thinking.

Learning tasks for the module – comprising 10 weekly activities each lasting 4 hours, were designed using CDIO Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences, so that students can learn the domain knowledge taught in other core chemical engineering modules in Stage 1B such as *Fluid Flow & Equipment*, and *Heat Transfer & Equipment* as part of horizontal integration in the spiral curriculum; as well as growth mindset, communication and teamwork covered earlier in Stage 1A. Based on the desired learning outcomes, all the learning tasks were designed to mimic or simulate real-world scenarios in the context of chemical engineering, so as to provide students with understanding of the job roles and tasks of chemical engineering graduates in various workplace settings, as well as situations whereby one needs to use SDL competency to complete a task at hand. Attainment of desired learning outcomes were achieved via the use of proper scaffoldings to support formative assessment in non-graded activities, and submissions of various reports on work done and reflection journal for summative assessment (CDIO Standard 11 Learning Assessments). There are also 2 debrief sessions – one mid-semester, and another at end-of-semester.

These learning tasks were also carefully sequenced to provide a transition from laboratory skills to process operation skills. Especially for process operation skills, the sequencing is important to set students up to use the SDL competency acquired in earlier sessions in later sessions, which involved working in various small-scale pilot plants.

Findings in Brief

Our spiral curriculum with SDL integrated was first rolled out in Academic Year 2018/2019 (AY18/19). Various surveys had been carried over the years on the students' learning experiences with SDL-infused activities. **One major survey is longitudinal in nature, where we follow the AY18/19 students from Stage 1A all the way until the complete their final year (capstone) project and internship in Year 3. In addition, the author also partnered with researchers from the Lee Kuan Yew Centre for Innovative Cities (LKYCIC) from the Singapore University of Technology & Design (SUTD) in another project involving volunteers from the same cohort of students, and he had leveraged on this partnership to have his LKYCIC partners conduct independent, separate studies on the importance of SDL as perceived by students (Mustafa, et al, 2022).**

Suffice to say that overall, a majority of students from various cohorts reported that the learning tasks are useful and results from the LKYCIC Focus Group Discussions also reaffirmed this point. Details of the work done over the years had been reported elsewhere (Wong & Cheah, 2022; Wong, Chua & Cheah, 2021; Cheah, 2020; Cheah, Wong & Yang, 2019). There are of course several areas of improvement mentioned by students and also recognized by the authors from the other surveys. These are addressed in various changes made, as explained in the next section.

Continual Improvement in SDL Integration

In SP, there is a mandatory module review every semester. We use CDIO Standard 12 Program Evaluation to guide the module review process (Cheah, Koh & Ng, 2013). Work done in the module were appraised based on findings from the student surveys and reviewed alongside relevant CDIO Standards, most notably Standard 1 The Context, Standard 2 Learning Outcomes, Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum, Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences, and Standard 11 Learning Assessment. We present here the work done to improve the module *Laboratory & Process Skills 2*; which had been implemented over the years:

- Make connections to previous semester (i.e. Stage 1A) on growth mindset as well as intrinsic motivation. Growth mindset got introduced into the curriculum via a new stakeholder module on ECG (*Education and Career Guidance*, compulsory for all students) that is an institution-wide response to the SkillsFuture Initiative. We also tweaked learning activities in *Laboratory & Process Skills 1* to orientate towards enhancing students' self-efficacy and hence intrinsic motivation.
- Provide guided questions tailored to specific learning tasks in various activities in *Laboratory & Process Skills 2*. This was done in response to our findings that students in general faced difficulties in applying the generic questions on SDL that we provided to specific experiments that they need to do.
- Provide URL links to the guided questions in addition to putting them in appendices of laboratory manuals, as a way of offering different ways that they can access the information. In this manner, we also reduce the cognitive loads of students as they can now click on each step of the SDL process to access the guidance questions.
- Design a new learning task that is easily integrates the need to exercise SDL competency in laboratory setting; by replacing an earlier learning task, that is very much 'standalone' in terms of content covered. The new learning task also allows natural transition to process operation skills, thus helping students to form connection between laboratory skills and process operation skills.
- Provide opportunity to apply SDL competency developed in a laboratory session in another follow-up session (within the same learning context with changes in the analysis that students need to perform) using a workbook approach.
- Conversion of an in-class lesson (on reading P&ID symbols and preparation of P&ID Lead Sheet) into e-learning format so that learning can be continued in the event of campus closure, and also allowing students to learn at their own pace (within assignment submission deadline), again using a workbook approach. (Author's Note: P&ID stands for piping and instrumentation diagram, which is the blueprint for a chemical plant represented using various symbols; and the lead sheet is like a picture dictionary

explaining what an item is in the chemical plant that is represented by the symbol. A chemical engineer or process technician uses a P&ID to walk around the plant and understand how the plant works)

- Provide students with sample reports from earlier cohorts on what constitute good submissions of Reflection Journal, and mistakes to avoid in preparation of P&ID Lead Sheet.
- Development of a limited functionality digital twin of a pilot plant, to allow students opportunity to practice line-tracing at home in event of campus closure. Scaffolds were provided in the 'campus closure' version so that students can again learn the topic at his/her own pace (within assignment submission deadline).
- Development of virtual learning environment in the forms of Interactive Video that helps students to continue applying SDL Competency in event of campus closure.
- And in the most recent semester, we also created a working template that takes students through the step-by-step process of SDL as per Figure 4.
- Lastly, we also started a new initiative to explicitly make students collaborate in the virtual space in their preparation of the P&ID Lead Sheet

It can be seen from some of the improvements mentioned above, represent efforts that are not only geared towards improving students' development of SDL competency, but also to ensure that learning can continue uninterrupted to the extent possible during a pandemic when campus closure is unavoidable.

Conclusion

This paper shared how we used the CDIO Framework to guide in the redesign on a module to integrate SDL into a 3-year curriculum. As we journey along in the effort of developing self-directed learners, we remain committed to make references to the CDIO Framework for guidance, especially in the spirit of continual improvement.

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